

Admissibility of the '*pay or consent*' model: between digital economic revolution and data protection modernisation

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1. Brief remarks on the evolution of business models and the exploitation of personal data processing value.

The evolution of business models in the digital age is a vast and complex topic, which is closely intertwined with the issue of personal data processing valorisation. The topic touches on many aspects: from the digital economy and technological innovation to the regulation of personal data, which cannot fail to take into account the continuous progress of the system and 'modernise' accordingly.

As is well known, the advent of the Internet and the rapid spread of digital technologies have profoundly transformed traditional business models. Starting in the 1990s and with the rise of Web 2.0 in the early 2000s, there has been a progressive digitisation of economic activities

¹ Authors: Luca Bolognini (L.Bolognini@istitutoprivacy.it), Lorenzo Covello, Giuseppe Fiordalisi

and the emergence of new business models based on the collection, analysis, and valorisation of data.

One of the most significant changes has been the shift from models based on the physical production and provision of goods/services to models centred on digital content, services and online platforms. Companies such as Amazon, Google, and Facebook (today Meta) have redefined the very concept of business, demonstrating how value can be generated not only by selling physical products, but also by exchanging and intermediating goods, services, content and information through digital platforms.

In parallel, a data-driven economy has developed, where economic value is increasingly linked to the ability to collect, analyse and create value from data. Data have become a key resource for businesses, used to customise services, improve operational efficiency, drive strategic decisions, and create new business models². Therefore, data plays a significant role for competitiveness and innovation.

In this factual framework, the regulation-factor is never neutral. It is worth underlining that every regulation, even the most technical or sectorial, brings with it and enhances one particular “vision of the world” and excludes, or at least penalises, other and different ones. The General Data Protection Regulation (Reg. (EU) 2016/679) does not escape this rule and stands as an instrument for raising the levels of protection and enhancement of individuals’ rights, freedoms, and interests worthy of protection in the European order, on the one hand, and as an element limiting the extension of other rights, freedoms, and interests. Among them, both positively (subject to enhancement) and negatively (subject to limitation), we undoubtedly find business freedoms, as well as freedom of expression and the right to information.

² On the new models of monetisation of personal data and their legal bases see L. Bolognini (2022). Economic Valorisation Of Personal Data And Legal Bases: For A "Digital Privacy New Deal", *Rivista Diritto, Economia e Tecnologie della Privacy* - ISSN 2239-7671 https://www.academia.edu/87494784/ECONOMIC_VALORISATION_OF_PERSONAL_DATA_AND_LEGAL_BASES_FOR_A_DIGITAL_PRIVACY_NEW_DEAL

Article 16 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, entitled 'Freedom to conduct a business' states: *'The freedom to conduct a business in accordance with Community law and national laws and practices is recognised'*. Article 41 of the Italian Constitution also enshrines freedom of economic initiative as a fundamental pillar, albeit within the limits set by the legal system and the necessary balancing with other rights, freedoms and interests: *'Private economic initiative is free. It may not be carried out in conflict with social utility or in such a way as to damage health, the environment, security, freedom or human dignity. The law determines the appropriate programmes and controls so that public and private economic activity may be directed and coordinated for social and environmental purposes'*. Freedom of enterprise is a fundamental right, of natural and legal persons, and, as such, it must be safeguarded and cannot be annihilated, neither by private powers, nor by the legislature, nor by public authorities called upon to enforce the law. It is common ground that the balancing of rights, freedoms and interests cannot be done in general and in the abstract, let alone in absolute terms, but must be done on a case-by-case basis.

In the balancing exercise between fundamental rights and freedoms and public interests, the principles of proportionality and reasonableness must guide. Reasonableness which, in the words of the Italian Constitutional Court ruling no. 1130 of 1988, *"far from entailing recourse to absolute and abstractly pre-established criteria of evaluation, is carried out through weightings relative to the proportionality of the means chosen"*; and then rises, this mixed and balanced mixture of proportionality and reasonableness, in the formula of the so-called "practical rationality", adopted by the Italian Constitutional Court in ruling no. 172 of 1996. Again in the words of the Italian Constitutional Court, in Judgment No. 85 of 2013 on the ILVA case, it is stated that *"all the fundamental rights protected by the Constitution are in a relationship of mutual integration and it is not possible, therefore, to identify one of them that has absolute prevalence over the others. Protection must always be 'systemic and not split into a series of uncoordinated and potentially conflicting rules' (Judgment No. 264*

of 2012). If this were not the case, there would be the unlimited expansion of one of the rights, which would become a 'tyrant' against the other constitutionally recognised and protected legal situations, which together constitute an expression of the dignity of the person".

And here we come to the subject of this paper, which requires considering the balance between fundamental rights and freedoms in relation to new models of socioeconomic relationships. **The concept of “exploitation of personal data processing value” does not refer to personal data itself as a commodity (this meaning would be incompatible with the protection of personal data as a fundamental right): it refers instead to the elaboration of personal data – “licensed” by data subjects – as an economic asset that can be given a commercial value**, representing an avant-garde model that certainly offers both opportunities and challenges. On the one hand, the economical valorisation of data can lead to innovations and personalised services that improve the user experience, on the other hand, there is the risk that such practices - if poorly executed with unethical and unlawful intentions - can infringe on the rights and freedoms of individuals and create inequalities.

A concrete example of a “digital age game scheme”, where companies seek to balance the exploitation of personal data processing value in accordance with Article 16 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU, with the protection of data subjects’ personal data, particularly in the European context underlying the GDPR, are 'pay or consent' models. These models are the subject matter of this paper. In practice, such models offer users, on the one hand, the option of paying a monetary consideration to access online content or services without having their personal data being processed for marketing and/or targeting purposes, and, on the other hand, the option of accessing the same content or services free of charge, whereby users are asked to consent to the processing of their personal data for advertising purposes, with the provision of the service being funded via targeted advertising. **It should also be emphasised, for the avoidance of doubt, that the 'pay or consent' models under consideration in this study do not include the profiling required to render**

personalised services requested by users and as such contractualised, which evidently fall under a completely different casuistry and legal basis (in particular, Art. 6(1)(b) GDPR).

Also in this light, Directive 2019/770/EC, Recital 24 provides the following: *“Digital content or digital services are often supplied also where the consumer does not pay a price but provides personal data to the trader. Such business models are used in different forms in a considerable part of the market. While fully recognising that the protection of personal data is a fundamental right and that therefore personal data cannot be considered as a commodity, this Directive should ensure that consumers are, in the context of such business models, entitled to contractual remedies. This Directive should, therefore, apply to contracts where the trader supplies, or undertakes to supply, digital content or a digital service to the consumer, and the consumer provides, or undertakes to provide, personal data”*.

The choice for users between paying for a service or obtaining the same service 'free of charge' paid by advertisers from the provider companies - if they consent to the use of their personal data for marketing and/or targeting purposes - is raising questions about the effectiveness of users' freedom of choice and autonomy.

For instance, can the protection of personal data go so far as to 'oblige' companies to provide online services free of charge or in some cases even go so far as to determine the fairness or appropriateness of the price if the alternative is the granting of consent to marketing and/or targeting? Is such an absolute approach to privacy adequate?

A further question concerns the type of online services, which one would like to be free or 'fair in price': could they be considered essential public services? Would the user, in the end, have an 'absolute' right to use services such as social networks or online news consultation offered by professionals, among others, for free or at a 'fair price'? And, in that case, who would be responsible for determining the 'fair price' or the classification of the public importance of the service?

2. The validity of consent as an alternative to payment in the light of European consumer and data protection law

In general, as already framed in the first part of this paper, it should be reaffirmed that the right to the protection of personal data is not an absolute right. Data protection shall be reconciled with other fundamental rights and freedoms, both of individuals and of other legal entities, as recognized by the Constitutions and, if we wish to remain Eurocentric, by the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union. Simply reading Recital 4 of the GDPR provides unequivocal confirmation: *"The processing of personal data should be designed to serve mankind. The right to the protection of personal data is not an absolute right; it must be considered in relation to its function in society and be balanced against other fundamental rights, in accordance with the principle of proportionality. This Regulation respects all fundamental rights and observes the freedoms and principles recognised in the Charter as enshrined in the Treaties, in particular the respect for private and family life, home and communications, the protection of personal data, freedom of thought, conscience and religion, freedom of expression and information, freedom to conduct a business, the right to an effective remedy and to a fair trial, and cultural, religious and linguistic diversity."*

If we combine Recital 4 GDPR with article 52 par. 1 of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, in the matter of the principle of proportionality to which legislators and institutions (and therefore also the Authorities) are bound in the first place, the picture is completed: *"Any limitation on the exercise of the rights and freedoms recognised by this Charter must be provided for by law and respect the essence of those rights and freedoms. Subject to the principle of proportionality, limitations may be made only if they are necessary and genuinely meet objectives of general interest recognised by the Union or the need to protect the rights and freedoms of others"*. It should be noted that this applies both to the protection of privacy and personal data, and vice versa, to safeguard the rights and freedoms of others, which cannot be suffocated by privacy and protection of personal data if interpreted and applied in a tyrannical and maximalist way.

Furthermore, with reference to the specific topic we are dealing with here, the legislator, first at EU level and then at national level, has already, more or less explicitly, recognized the legitimacy of commercial practices implemented through schemes such as the 'pay or consent' model under consideration, not defining *ex ante* the nullity or annullability of such contractual relationships, but subjecting them, in addition to the ordinary rules governing contractual matters and those in force concerning the protection of personal data, to the consumer protection legislation³.

The mentioned EU Directive 2019/770 and, consequently, the amended Italian Legislative Decree No. 206 of 6 September 2005 (the Italian 'Consumer Code'), have the virtue of providing for the personal data vs. service synallagma as a legitimate contractual arrangement, therefore recognised and deserving of protection by the legal system. In addition, the Consumer rights Omnibus Directive 2019/2161 expressly mention that a service can be provided in consideration of the provision and use of personal data. The legislative recognition of the legitimacy of the synallagmatic relationship of personal data being processed in order to fund the provision of online services makes it possible to affirm that "*these data - and the metadata associated with them - constitute an asset subject to economic and legal relations*"⁴. The legitimacy of the contract having as its object such a synallagmatic relationship is also recognised, as detailed in the following paragraphs, in the provisions and Guidelines of more than one European national Data Protection Authority.

³ On the other hand, it is not the first time that jurists first, and then legislators, in the inevitable pursuit of law in the progress of society, have used the instrument of interpretation to assess the legitimacy of the practices and usages implemented by citizens. Suffice it to think of the so-called *lex mercatoria*, defined by one of the most illustrious jurists our legal system has ever known as "*a law created by the entrepreneurial class, without the mediation of the legislative power of States, and formed by rules intended to uniformly regulate, beyond the political unity of States, the commercial relations that are established within the economic unity of markets*" F. Galgano, in *Diritto civile e commerciale*, I, Padua, 1999, pp. 89 ff. Again, as noted *illo tempore* by certain doctrine, "*The application of the lex mercatoria to electronic commerce is therefore a phenomenon already in progress, whose fundamental manifestations seem to consist of the extreme objectification of the exchange, through uniform contractual practices, which also convey law through technological choices*" G. Finocchiaro, in *Diritto di Internet*, Third Edition, Bologna, 2020, pp. 19 ff.

⁴ G. Resta, V. Zeno-Zencovich, in *Volontà e consenso nella fruizione dei servizi in rete*, in *Rivista trimestrale di diritto e procedura civile*, Anno LXXII, Fasc. 2, 2018, p. 416.

Furthermore, personalised advertising has been considered a legitimate business model by Courts and the EU regulators, despite the fact that requirements were imposed. It is worth mentioning CJEU (C-252/21) 147, affirming that “[...] the fact that the operator of an online social network, as controller, holds a dominant position on the social network market does not, as such, prevent the users of that social network from validly giving their consent [...]” and that “[Facebook] users must be free to refuse individually, in the context of the contractual process, to give their consent to particular data processing operations not necessary for the performance of the contract, without being obliged to refrain entirely from using the service offered by the online social network operator, which means that those users are to be offered, if necessary⁵ for an appropriate fee, an equivalent alternative not accompanied by such data processing operations [...]”.

Here, wanting to take into consideration the legitimacy profiles of the phenomenon of the economic valorisation of the processing of personal data in the context of the 'pay or consent' model negotiation scheme, it becomes crucial to examine and interpret the relevant provisions of the GDPR. The question moves towards a necessary enquiry into the lawfulness of the transaction involving the processing of personal data in exchange for services, and this enquiry, in the light of the provisions of the GDPR, must primarily focus on the issue of freedom of consent to processing.

The issue in Europe concerns the concept of "freely given" consent (Art. 7.4 GDPR) to the use of personal data. In essence, consent should be a free, specific and informed expression of the individual's will, but, still, would the 'pay or consent' model introduce a coercive dynamic? In other words, could access to online services free of charge, conditional on consent, implicitly push users/data subjects to consent to the use of their personal data even when they might prefer not to do so? What factors must be considered in assessing whether consent is 'freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous'?

⁵ Interestingly, only the English translation of this decision uses this phrasing. The authoritative French and German language versions of the judgment focus on appropriateness of the fee, with no reference to “necessity.”

3. European positions: a multi-lane road

There is the need to analyse the consent given under the "pay or okay" model in light of the European data protection discipline, in order to assess the lawfulness of the “negotiating scheme” in question. The Court of Justice of the European Union, with its decision CJEU (C-252/21) 147 on “Meta Platforms and Others (General terms of use of a social network)”, and more than one European Data Protection Authority involved on the subject⁶, have contributed to elaborating a series of criteria and requirements whose fulfilment would guarantee the data controller to act in compliance with the regulations in force. These criteria – such as the similarity or equivalence of the services to which the user would have access by choosing to give his/her consent or, instead, to pay the required fee for the service, or the infungibility of the services and the reasonableness of the price – although expressed in almost all the decisions published to date on the subject, can be interpreted and applied differently.

Guidance on the topic by the European Data Protection Board (EDPB) could promote harmonisation and legal certainty, if done right. A mandate for an opinion and guidelines has already been issued. The Data Protection Authorities of Norway⁷, Hamburg and the Netherlands have requested an opinion focusing on large platforms which is expected to be published in the coming weeks.

Pending the EDPB's orientation on the matter, it seems useful to briefly elaborate on some of the criteria developed to date by the Member States Data Protection Authorities, also in the light of the Italian local orientation.

⁶ Examples include, but are not limited to, the Austrian Data Protection Authority's Order of 20 August 2019 as well as the subsequent FAQs produced on the subject by the same Authority in 2022 (cf. FAQ zum Thema Cookies und Datenschutz); the evaluation criteria published on 16 May 2022 by the French Data Protection Authority, the CNIL (cf. Cookie walls : la CNIL publie des premiers critères d'évaluation); the Order of 23 March 2023 of the German Data Protection Authority (cf. DSK_Beschluss_Bewertung_von_Pur-Abomodellen_auf_Websites.pdf (datenschutzkonferenz-online.de) and, again, the Order of the Danish Data Protection Authority of 8 February 2023 (cf. Gul og Gratis' brug af cookie walls (datatilsynet.dk).

⁷ Below is the link to the Norwegian Data Protection Authority's press release: The Norwegian Data [Protection Authority asks the EDPB for a formal opinion on 'pay or okay' | The Norwegian Data Protection Authority \(datatilsynet.no\)](#), (last visited 11 February 2024).

3.1. The criteria of equivalence and infungibility of services

First, it is necessary to enucleate what is meant by the concepts of equivalence and infungibility of the services outlined in the Italian context by sources of case law and decisions of the Italian Data Protection Authority (hereinafter, also referred to as the "Garante Authority"). The equivalence of services refers to the possibility offered to users to access contents or services having identical or similar characteristics through different access options, without necessarily requiring their consent for marketing and/or profiling purposes to the use of cookies or other trackers in order to be able to access such services. In other words, the user's freedom of choice between giving consent or not is considered valid when there is an alternative that allows a similar service or content to be used, regardless of the access mode chosen.

This concept can be found in Decision no. 231 of 10 June 2021, published in the Italian Official Gazette no. 163 of 9 July 2021, issued by the Garante Authority containing the "Guidelines on the use of cookies"⁸.

In the aforementioned decision, the Garante Authority specified that the use of the 'cookie wall', which requires users to accept cookies in order to access content, is generally inadmissible. An exception may only be considered in specific circumstances and in any case assessed on a case-by-case basis, where the site publisher allows access to equivalent/similar content or services without requiring consent for the use of cookies or other tracking mechanisms. Basically, the aforementioned Guidelines do not explicitly consider the 'pay or consent' model to be illegitimate, in the sense of not ruling on its merits.

⁸ <https://www.garanteprivacy.it/web/guest/home/docweb/-/docweb-display/docweb/9677876#english>

As for the principle of 'fungibility of the service', expressed in the Italian Supreme Court of Cassation's ruling no. 17278 of 2 July 2018⁹, it implies that the service itself can be considered fungible if the user can give up the service without suffering a heavy sacrifice. In essence, by virtue of the aforementioned principle, website operators would be permitted to require consent to the processing of personal data for advertising purposes as a condition for accessing certain services, provided that the consent is given freely, specifically, informedly and unequivocally for those purposes. Fungibility is based on the possibility of substituting the service with other similar ones available, without this entailing a significant burden for the user. In other words, the Sentence *de qua* establishes that the more the service offered is essential and indispensable for the user, therefore infungible and not available through other sources, the less legitimate it is to make it subject to the condition of granting consent.

3.2. The criterion of price reasonableness

More than one National Data Protection Authority¹⁰, ruling on the lawfulness of the 'pay or consent' model, have stated that, in order to consider the consent possibly given by the data subject as free and in accordance with the provisions of the GDPR, the pay-as-you-go alternative proposed by the data controller must be able to be deemed as "reasonable", in

⁹ Italian Supreme Court of Cassation's ruling no. 17278 of 2 July 2018: "The Court considers, in the context of the application of the aforementioned art. 23, that the answer to the question cannot be unequivocal and, that is to say, that the conditioning cannot always and in any event be taken for granted and must instead be considered to be all the more present, the more the service offered by the operator of the internet site is both inalienable and indispensable for the person concerned, which certainly cannot be said to be the case in the hypothesis of the offer of a generic information service of the kind at issue, since it is clearly information that can be easily acquired by other means, possibly through sites subject to payment, if not through recourse to printed publications, with the result that that service may well be renounced without a heavy sacrifice. Therefore, the argument put forward by the court of merit cannot be shared, according to which, by giving credence to the thesis put forward by the Guarantor, one would end up "delineating a sort of tout court obligation, for the portal operator, to offer its services in any event, regardless of the user's consent to the processing of personal data": and, in essence, to thus oblige the portal operator to renounce the economic benefit of the operation he carries out, deriving from the advertising activity carried out through the use of the personal data acquired. Nothing, in fact, prevents the operator of the site - of course, we repeat, in a case such as the one at issue, concerning a service that is neither infungible nor indispensable - from denying the service offered to those who do not wish to receive promotional messages, whereas what he is prohibited from doing is using the personal data to administer or have administered advertising information to those who have not actually expressed the will to receive it. In short, the law does not prohibit the exchange of personal data, but it does require that such an exchange be the result of full and in no way coerced consent."

¹⁰ See footnote 6.

the sense of not being disproportionate, completely unrealistic, unreasonably high or so high that the registered person does not really in practice have a choice (or in other words, that the fee does not create a situation of “significant economic duress”). While the conduct of a teleological investigation makes it easy to detect the underlying rationale of the criterion under examination, an accurate literal interpretation poses more than one critical issue.

Arguing this, it is clear that the European Data Protection Authorities wish to avoid a situation where the data subject, having to decide whether to give consent or pay an disproportionate price, is *de facto* forced to restrict his or her right to personal data protection in order to use a given service¹¹. Nevertheless, the criterion of the reasonableness of the price, and particularly the use of the adjective "reasonable", although appreciable in its rationale, raises more than one reflection on its application.

Wanting to proceed in a logical-juridical order, two questions should, for example, be explored in greater depth. On the one hand, in fact, it is necessary to identify the given characteristics that, if present, make a given price 'reasonable'. On the other hand, an enquiry as to who is the subject deputed to review the possible unreasonableness of the price demanded as an alternative to consent in relation to the 'pay or consent' model is inescapable.

With reference to the first question, it suffices to represent how, in a liberal-capitalist society such as today's European one, the price is reasonable as it is perceived as fair by the consumer, and it can be considered not disproportionate by reference to the value of the particular service to consumers as well as by comparing the price to competing products and services on the market. Thus, it could be said that the market regulates itself, through the various interactions between supply and demand, given a given good or service. To take a

¹¹ On possible imbalance and appropriateness of price, see Mikołaj Barczentewicz, 'Pay or consent': Personalized ads, the rules and what's next, IAPP Portal, 20 November 2023 <https://iapp.org/news/a/pay-or-consent-personalized-ads-the-rules-and-whats-next/>

trivial example, the fashion products of luxury brands have a perceived intrinsic value to the consumer many times higher than their production cost.

In relation to the second question, on the other hand, given that the review of the reasonableness of the price cannot fall within the scope of the powers of the National Data Protection Authorities¹² (which shall have a limited ability to assess the appropriateness of the price, for instance restricted to confirm that the price is not disproportionate or creates a situation of "significant economic duress"), it is essential to identify the subject to whom this control should be entrusted. While awaiting the publication of the EDPB's guidance on the 'pay or consent' model, what stands out is that the data controller interested in using the 'pay or consent' model, in an imbalanced mixture of business risk and accountability, will have to determine autonomously the reasonable price for using its service, without being aware of the entity by which this price will be reviewed or of the criteria the latter will use.

3.3. Applicability of the same criteria to e-privacy and DMA disciplines

As a final reflection, one might wonder whether the reasoning above – with its criteria and conditions, still uncertain but already visible in the European legal framework - is also applicable to e-privacy and Digital Markets Act disciplines. Directive 2002/58/EC (the e-privacy Directive, on privacy and electronic communications) clarifies in its Recital no. 17: *"For the purposes of this Directive, consent of a user or subscriber, regardless of whether the latter is a natural or a legal person, should have the same meaning as **the data subject's consent as defined and further specified in Directive 95/46/EC** [to be intended, now, as the GDPR]. Consent may be given by any appropriate method enabling a freely given specific and*

¹² In this regard, it is represented that, firstly, no such power and responsibility can be found in the legislation regulating the work of such Authorities. Secondly, the attribution of the assessment in question to the National Supervisory Authorities could lead to different decisions as to the reasonableness of the same price, applied for the same service but in different European countries, with a consequent potential violation of the European principles of free competition and, where appropriate, damage to the single European market.

informed indication of the user's wishes, including by ticking a box when visiting an Internet website."

Also, Article 5 par. 2 of the Digital Markets Act (DMA, Reg. (EU) 2022/1925) provides that the *“gatekeeper shall not do any of the following: (a) process, for the purpose of providing online advertising services, personal data of end users using services of third parties that make use of core platform services of the gatekeeper; (b) combine personal data from the relevant core platform service with personal data from any further core platform services or from any other services provided by the gatekeeper or with personal data from third-party services; (c) cross-use personal data from the relevant core platform service in other services provided separately by the gatekeeper, including other core platform services, and vice versa; and (d) sign in end users to other services of the gatekeeper in order to combine personal data, unless the end user has been presented with the specific choice and has given consent **within the meaning of Article 4, point (11), and Article 7 of Regulation (EU) 2016/679”**.*

In e-privacy and DMA scenarios, specific consents are required for data processing which falls within the respective disciplines. One can ask, therefore, whether the above analysed criteria and conditions for 'GDPR pay or consent' model are also applicable in the case of specific consents imposed by these additional rules. In both cases, it is clearly underlined - by e-privacy directive as well as Art. 5 par. 2 DMA - that consent must be intended as defined in the GDPR: therefore, in the opinion of the Authors, the same possible conditioning criteria of admissibility of the alternative choice between payment and consent, if valid for the GDPR, should also apply to cases of e-privacy and/or DMA consents.

4. Conclusions

In conclusion, as emerged from the pronouncements of the National Data Protection Authorities and courts referred to in this review, and pending the EDPB's guidance on the matter, it is important to emphasise that the 'pay or consent' model - with appropriate adjustments and respecting criteria of equivalence and fungibility of services at reasonable prices - may represent, in the Authors' opinion, a valid and legitimate approach in the digital ecosystem, consistent with the current legal framework of the European Union. After all, the model under consideration introduces an element of choice for users. The model would make it possible to sustain – both on the demand side and on the supply side – a wide range of online services. A mechanism capable of balancing, on the one hand, the business needs of the companies providing the services and, on the other, the user's choice to make use of them by granting consent or, alternatively, by paying the required fee which, unless it is a so-called essential public service (an assessment that should be referred to the legislator), could be determined autonomously by the provider in the exercise of its right to freedom of enterprise.

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